

Supplementary Data for:

Biogeographic history of pigeons and doves drives the origin and diversification of their parasitic
body lice

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SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Table S1 (Excel file). Metadata for samples of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroup taxa used for whole genome sequencing and subsequent assembly for phylogenetic analysis.

Table S2. Secondary calibrations based on codivergence events used to estimate divergence times of dove body lice. Dates are based on the 95% HPD intervals from divergence estimates of doves from Boyd et al. (2022).

Louse split	Host split	Date range
<i>Coloceras</i> sp. - <i>Coloceras</i> sp.	<i>Petrophassa rufipennis</i> - <i>Petrophassa albipennis</i>	1.7-16.8 MY
<i>Physconelloides ceratoceps 1</i> - <i>Physcondelloides ceratoceps 5</i>	<i>Leptotila jamaicensis</i> - <i>Leptotila rufaxilla</i>	1.8-22.4 MY
<i>Physconelloides zenaidurae</i> - <i>Physconelloides wisemani</i>	<i>Zenaida macroura</i> - <i>Zenaida asiatica</i>	2.8-15.8 MY
<i>Campanulotes bidentatus</i> - <i>Campanulotes compar</i>	<i>Columba palumbus</i> - <i>Columba livia</i>	3.9-21.0 MY
<i>Campanulotes</i> sp. - <i>Campanulotes</i> sp.	<i>Phaps histrionica</i> - <i>Phaps elegans</i>	4.8-20.7 MY
<i>Coloceras</i> sp. - <i>Coloceras</i> sp.	<i>Turtur chalcospilos</i> - <i>Turtur tympanistria</i>	5.1-29.7 MY
<i>Campanulotes</i> sp. - <i>Campanulotes</i> sp.	<i>Geophaps plumifera</i> - <i>Geophaps smithii</i>	5.4-12.9 MY

Table S3. Normalized Robinson-Foulds distances between pairs of phylogenetic trees estimated from alignments of nuclear genes from dove body lice and outgroup taxa.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
2	0.0787								
3	0.0112	0.0899							
4	0.0337	0.0899	0.0449						
5	0.0000	0.0787	0.0112	0.0337					
6	0.0337	0.0899	0.0449	0.0000	0.0337				
7	0.0562	0.0337	0.0674	0.0674	0.0562	0.0674			
8	0.0112	0.0899	0.0000	0.0449	0.0112	0.0449	0.0674		
9	0.0000	0.0787	0.0112	0.0337	0.0000	0.0337	0.0562	0.0112	
10	0.0337	0.0899	0.0449	0.0000	0.0337	0.0000	0.0674	0.0449	0.0337

- 1: Concatenated tree (max 60% missing data, all sites)
- 2: ASTRAL tree (max 90% missing data, 1+2 sites)
- 3: ASTRAL tree (max 90% missing data, all sites)
- 4: Concatenated tree (max 90% missing data, 1+2 sites)
- 5: Concatenated tree (max 90% missing data, all sites)
- 6: Concatenated tree (max 60% missing data, 1+2 sites)
- 7: ASTRAL tree (max 60% missing data, 1+2 sites)
- 8: ASTRAL tree (max 60% missing data, all sites)
- 9: Concatenated tree (no filtering, all sites)
- 10: Concatenated tree (no filtering, 1+2 sites)

Table S4. Results from Approximately Unbiased tests between nuclear phylogenies of dove body lice. All trees were compared to the most likely tree estimated from a concatenated alignment (60% max missing data). DeltaL indicates the difference in log-likelihood from the maximum.

	LogL	DeltaL	p-AU
1	-61883684.9800	0.0001	0.4490
2	-61894778.6000	11094.0000	0.000032
3	-61892276.9100	8591.9000	1.55E-42
4	-61884938.2400	1253.3000	0.0003
5	-61883684.9800	0.0000	0.5150
6	-61884938.2400	1253.3000	0.0004
7	-61891621.5400	7936.6000	0.0003
8	-61892276.9100	8591.9000	1.49E-42
9	-61883684.9800	0.0003	0.4920
10	-61884938.24	1253.3	0.0002

- 1: Concatenated tree (max 60% missing data, all sites)
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- 5: Concatenated tree (max 90% missing data, all sites)
- 6: Concatenated tree (max 60% missing data, 1+2 sites)
- 7: ASTRAL tree (max 60% missing data, 1+2 sites)
- 8: ASTRAL tree (max 60% missing data, all sites)
- 9: Concatenated tree (no filtering, all sites)
- 10: Concatenated tree (no filtering, 1+2 sites)

Table S5. Comparisons between different models of historical biogeography for dove body lice, including rates of dispersal (d), extinction (e), and a jump-dispersal parameter (j).

Model	LnL	# parameters	d	e	j	AICc	Weighted AICc
DEC	-109	2	0.37	0.012	0	222.3	4.00E-09
DEC+J	-89.91	3	0.13	1.00E-12	0.04	186.2	0.27
DIVALIKE	-110.7	2	0.56	2.50E-08	0	225.7	7.30E-10
DIVALIKE+J	-88.94	3	0.14	1.00E-12	0.039	184.3	0.72
BAYAREALIKE	-93.77	3	0.12	1.00E-12	0.047	193.9	0.0057
BAYAREALIKE+J	-93.77	3	0.12	1.00E-12	0.047	193.9	0.0057

Table S6. Lowest-cost reconciliations from a Jane analysis comparing phylogenies of doves and their body lice. Reconciliations were run under the default cost parameters (Cospeciation: 0, Duplication: 1, Duplication and Host Switch: 2, Loss: 1, Failure to diverge: 1).

# of solutions	Cospeciations	Duplications	Host switches	Losses	Failures to diverge
7350	19	3	35	7	6
4205	20	3	34	9	6
7939	19	2	35	8	6
6962	20	2	35	8	6
602	21	2	34	10	6
727	20	1	36	7	6
700	21	1	35	9	6

Figure S2. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroup taxa based on a concatenated alignment of 2,367 orthologous genes with 60% maximum missing data (40% complete). Branch support values are shown above associated branches, and include SH-aLRT, bootstrap, gene concordance, and site concordance factor values, respectively. Branch lengths given in nucleotide substitutions per site.

Figure S3. Species tree of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa summarized from 2,367 genes trees estimated from alignments with 60% maximum missing data (40% complete). Local posterior probability support values are shown above associated branches. Internal branch lengths are in coalescent units. Branch lengths of terminal branches are not meaningful.

Figure S4. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa based on a concatenated alignment of 2,367 orthologous genes with 10% maximum missing data (90% complete). Branch support values are shown above associated branches, and include SH-aLRT, bootstrap, gene concordance, and site concordance factor values, respectively.

3.0

Figure S5. Species tree of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa summarized from 2,367 genes trees estimated from alignments with 10% maximum missing data (90% complete). Local posterior probability support values are shown above associated branches. Internal branch lengths are in coalescent units. Branch lengths of terminal branches are not meaningful.

Figure S6. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa based on a concatenated alignment of 2,367 orthologous genes with no filtering based on missing data (all sites). Branch support values are shown above associated branches, and include SH-aLRT and bootstrap values, respectively.

Figure S7. Saturation plots for a concatenated alignment of 2,367 nuclear genes from dove body lice (40% complete alignment).

Figure S8. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa based on a concatenated alignment of 2,367 orthologous genes with 60% maximum missing data (40% complete) and only first and second codon positions. Branch support values are shown above associated branches, and include SH-aLRT, bootstrap, gene concordance, and site concordance factor values, respectively.

Figure S9. Species tree of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa summarized from 2,367 genes trees estimated from alignments with 60% maximum missing data (40% complete) and only first and second codon positions. Local posterior probability support values are shown above associated branches. Internal branch lengths are in coalescent units. Branch lengths of terminal branches are not meaningful.

Figure S10. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa based on a concatenated alignment of 2,367 orthologous genes with 10% maximum missing data (60% complete) and only first and second codon positions. Branch support values are shown above associated branches, and include SH-aLRT, bootstrap, gene concordance, and site concordance factor values, respectively.

Figure S11. Species tree of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa summarized from 2,367 genes trees estimated from alignments with 10% maximum missing data (90% complete) and only first and second codon positions. Local posterior probability support values are shown above associated branches. Internal branch lengths are in coalescent units. Branch lengths of terminal branches are not meaningful.

Figure S12. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa based on first and second codon position sites in a concatenated alignment of 2,367 orthologous genes with no filtering based on missing data. Branch support values are shown above associated branches, and include SH-aLRT and bootstrap values, respectively.

Figure S13. Dated phylogenetic tree of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroups taxa from MCMCTree. 95% Highest Posterior Density (HPD) intervals are shown as blue bars at each node. Secondary calibration points inferred from host-parasite codivergence events are indicated with red circles.

Figure S14. Dated phylogenetic tree of dove body lice, galliform lice, and outgroups taxa from a second run of MCMCTree. 95% Highest Posterior Density (HPD) intervals are shown as blue bars at each node.

Figure S15. Dated phylogenetic tree of dove body lice, galliform lice, and outgroups taxa from the LSD2 method in IQTree2.

Figure S16. Dated phylogenetic tree of dove body lice and galliform lice under a DEC model in BioGeoBEARS. The DEC model was the best model with the jump (+J) parameters. Branch lengths are scaled to millions of years. Circles at the tips show the current known distributions of that taxon according to one of five biogeographic regions: Africa (green), Australasia (red), Eurasia (yellow), North America (dark blue), South America (light blue). Taxa found in both North and South America are shown with a medium-dark blue. Pie charts at each node indicate the likelihood the ancestor lived in a particular biogeographic region.

Figure S17. A phylogenetic reconciliation between doves (black lines) and their body lice (blue lines) from Jane. Cospeciation events are indicated by open red circles, duplications by filled red circles, host switches by filled yellow circles and arrows, losses by dotted lines, and failures to diverge by jagged lines.

Figure S18. A biogeographically-constrained phylogenetic reconciliation between doves (gray lines) and their body lice (black and orange lines) from MOWGLI. Pie charts at nodes indicate the likely ancestral ranges for doves (large pie charts) and lice (smaller pie charts). Cospeciation events are indicated by splits as black lines, host switches by dotted orange lines and arrows, and losses by open black circles.

Figure S19. Distribution of Procrustes residuals from randomized associations in comparisons of dove wing louse and dove body louse phylogenies in PACo. The observed residual value is indicated with an orange vertical line.

Figure S20. Distribution of Procrustes residuals from randomized phylogenies in comparisons of dove wing louse and dove body louse phylogenies in PACo. The observed residual value is indicated with an orange vertical line.

Figure S21. Maximum likelihood phylogeny of dove body lice, landfowl lice, and outgroup taxa based on the mitochondrial *cox1* gene. Bootstrap support values are shown above each branch. Branch lengths given in nucleotide substitutions per site.

Figure S22. Proportion of cumulative speciation events in dove body lice that are attributed to host switches versus cospeciation events over time. X-axis indicates binds of time in millions of years before present.